

P 56 3.23.18

#1

— P 56

#2

← P 56

#3

← P 56

Phospha

GapdH

3.27.18

#1

#2

#3

Total S6 3.23.18

#1

#2

#3

Total
Gap 471

3.27.18

#1 ✓

#2 ✓

#3 ✓